

Impact of Mathematics on Society's Development

C. Jhansi Devi

Lecturer in Mathematics, New Science College, Hyderabad.

Abstract:

The subject of Mathematics emerged as a leading discipline in the domain of Sciences. Mathematics becomes central to the growth of other disciplines of study like Humanities, Social Sciences, Sciences. From the perspective of Natural Sciences, Nature embraces its patterns gave lot of scope in the evolving several of mathematical theorems. It is observed, Mathematics plays a predominant role in measurement, quantifying the data in providing logical derivations with accuracy. Given the importance of Mathematics in overall development of the society, different political regimes from time to time gave priority in formulating certain policies. This helped the civilization in changing its nature from time to time alongside with the scientific developments by using the mathematical tools. Therefore, the present paper portrays contribution of Mathematics in the growth of society in terms of socio-economical political domain.

Keywords: Embedded, Computation, Political Socialization, quantitative sophistication, Algorithm, Symmetry, Poverty, Unemployment.

Introduction

Mathematics as a discipline of study contributes much to the development of society in terms of knowledge creation by taking cognizance of other streams of Sciences which together simplify the operations which are essential methods in establishing a system. The study of Mathematics is very much essential in the changing nature of the world in formulation of certain economic policies backed by political ideologies which are surrounded by the typical interests of certain groups which employ their systems in maximizing their profits by lobbying certain interest groups. The pertinent question over the subject of Mathematics concerning the phenomenon of growth and development operates parallel to the political system as well as to the economic system. It is to be noted that nature itself forms certain patterns which are highly used in mathematical perspectives, in another sense, Nature embraces Mathematics much. A close observation of nature gives us a sense of symmetry around us embedded with different patterns. The geographical changes observed in nature such as the seasons, changes in the days, and the biological patterns relating to the shape of plants, trees, flowers, and fruits give a good lead to the study involving Mathematics by observing the patterns. For ex. shapes, symmetry, and patterns etc.

Concept of Mathematics

Mathematics being one of the branches of Sciences enjoys a significant place and plays a major role among other disciplines in analyzing the data collected for the studies. Though it primarily deals with the operational aspects of the numbers but also it helps in solving certain problems by engaging in computations and calculations. It is stated that Mathematics is the science of

Measurement, Quantity, and Magnitude and it compiles data with a lot of precision with logical conclusions.

Society and Mathematics

Human society is a complex entity with a lot of diversity in terms of culture, ethnicity, religion, and colour, sharing a large geography territory with regulatory bodies which are bound to follow certain principles of governance to exercise political authority in meeting the economic expectations of different groups. To maintain harmonious distribution of resources available within the territory, which is to be dispersed according to the proportion that exists in terms of culture and population. In the distribution of wealth in a proportional manner, certain methods are utilized from the domain of Mathematics. The allocations made through the mathematical calculations help the system to maintain equilibrium among the groups. As a whole, the society runs on the concept of cooperative nature by each group displaying social skills of negotiation, interaction, and pressure politics. To maintain non-coercive nature, the state takes the advantage of mathematical knowledge in projecting the growth rates, the amount of business carried, and the number of industrial outlets contributing to the economy effectively collaborating while making the allocations to the respective social groups. Thus maintaining equitable allocations to the respective social groups. Comprehensively, in maintaining the pace of development, the subject of Mathematics facilitates the political and social structures in projecting the outcomes which are navigated by establishing effective communications like transport, electricity, science, and technology. As a whole, Mathematics made its presence in measuring the progress of society impeccably.

Intellectuality vs Mathematics

The growth of the intellectuality of an individual, irrespective of their age, refers much to Mathematics. It plays a greater role in the intellectual development of a child by exposing them to solutions, sequences, and numeracy. Mathematics makes a child's brain more active when assigned to solving problems and mental activities. This process makes the human brain more constructive and creative to become critical in all faculties of psychological growth. Mathematics helps the individual to be effective in terms of calculations of time, money, speech, and thought. However, it makes an individual very strong in terms of willpower and helps in discovering many things in himself. Mathematics also builds a lot of confidence among individuals in terms of self-reliance, and self-dependence and also helps them to possess the ability of patience.

The intellectual development of an individual can be enhanced in any other disciplines in preparing them to obtain knowledge in the domain of technical and applied sciences ex. engineering, architecture, banking, business, accountancy, surveying, and agriculture which have the prerequisite nature of mathematical knowledge. In a simple sense, it requires knowledge of Mathematics in carrying out any study in the domains mentioned above. According to pierce "Mathematics is the Science which draws necessary conclusions". Extension to this the study of psychology draws its strength much from Mathematics by developing certain tests in analyzing the mind which is assisted by the accurate expressions of thoughts. Though Mathematics is commonly concerned with mere functions of subtractions, additions, multiplicity and divides it has many other functions for a common man in leading a better life for a highly evolved society.

Mathematics and Social Development

The Aristotelian approach of understanding man as a social animal is aptly related to the process of political socialization where a large section of the society represents different social identities by sharing the same geographical spaces conditioned by resource possession. In the broader sense establishment of much accepted political system endorsed by good governance can run a system by analyzing the available resources by employing certain mathematical methods in the allocation of resources proportional to the respective social groups. The crucial and unique role in human societies is attributed to Mathematics and evolving more acceptable strategies for development with a holistic approach to addressing the problems of mankind. The absence of the process without employing mathematical theories in resource allocation had witnessed a lot of equilibrium further leading to huge gaps between rich and poor. The new advanced data analysis developed through mathematical theorems helped in the process, of how the wealth is concentrated in a few ethnic/caste groups, to help the deprived communities to put forward the demands for equality in terms of resource allocation and sharing political power. In the other sense, members of society who are associated with the process of governance organize the resources available and in turn allocate the resources to the domains which are to be promoted for immediate development. It is inevitable for policymakers to analyze the data on resources by employing certain mathematical tools in convincing the public to have their support to make their way to power. It has become a necessary evil as opined by John Locke to depend upon the domain of Mathematics for achieving political power. Therefore, the policymakers realized the importance of Mathematics in the process of development of society which is understandably more transparent in terms of the implementation of certain welfare schemes.

The Changing World: The Relevance of Mathematics

It is evident from daily experiences that the usage of Mathematics is wide enough in the fields of research, data analysis, and further matter every sphere of human activity. Knowing Mathematics makes one's own life satisfying and gives a feeling of empowerment. From the experiences of people in the day-to-day, life is much engrossed and intertwined with technology and Mathematics. It can be noted from the transactions like the choice of purchases, finding an effective policy of insurance, and associated decisions concerning voting patterns make them a prerequisite in the way of quantitative sophistication. For example, the studies conducted in terms of exit polls are analyzed from the data collected from different parts of the constituency, to promote an idea that helps the voter in critically opting for his choice of the election with his quantifiable skills.

Cultural Heritage and Mathematics

The archaeologists in their attempt to establish the periods of certain monumental and archival evidence effectively use mathematical tools in assessing the achievements, aspects of aesthetics, and recreational aspects of Mathematics and its relationship with science and technology used to inform citizens scientifically. For instance, the kind of awareness promoted in the field of mathematical education tremendously gives us an understanding of the intellectual abilities of cross-sections of society that are effectively tapped where lakhs of engineering graduates are produced in a year. This indicator itself shows mathematical education is producing a huge chunk of intelligent citizens dramatically posing a challenge to

the policymakers in creating a job market for graduates. This process is creating huge pressure on policymakers to devise certain programs which would accommodate these graduates. The critics of the policies suggest certain alternatives and project the probable numbers of returns which would help much to the contribution of the gross development product of the country. There is another observation from the critical perspective, many of the students who pursue Mathematics courses and Mathematics embedded courses like engineering are unable to be placed in the job market in their respective subjects' domain after having intensive mathematical analytical skills. This trend poses a grave threat in terms of the unemployable nature of the government and pushes these graduates to resort to taking up professions that are not related to their domain background. This is very disheartening when the potential skills of youngsters are not properly being utilized as they had aspired to pursue work for lifelong as mathematicians, statisticians, engineers, and scientists. The scope for Mathematics is very wide when one closely observes how technological advancement is highly dependent upon Mathematics. This poses a huge ethical question to the intellectuals of the society and the politicians for not effectively managing young minds of the society who are thoroughly trained and motivated. We have been witnessing mushrooming of a lot of engineering colleges and institutions but in one sense, it promotes and produces technocrats the society but the socio-economic system of the society is unable to absorb them in their respective domains which is a negative symptom in the society, and creates an element of unrest. In such kind of situation, it is the role of policymakers in utilizing the services of the young potential group which would significantly give an impetus to the economy and enhances opportunities and chances for shaping the future on par with the developed societies. Competence in Mathematics has twofold benefits, one being the individual becoming more critical and productive and second, correspondingly contributing to the welfare of the society. It is a known fact that competence in Mathematics keeps the doors of opportunities open for a productive future and the absence of competence would permanently keep the doors closed for a lifetime. But the Indian scenario is quite contradictory pushing the intellectual domain of the mathematical community to a situation of bankruptcy in terms of resources.

Mathematics and its Relation to Professional Development

Mathematics plays an important role in shaping the individual for a better future providing a way to develop the critical ability to assess the situation in pursuing a better study in preparing himself/herself to be able to obtain a profession which correspondingly helps the course he/she completed gives a perfect interest driven profession. For instance, analyzing the data of growth and development, statistics and econometrics are essential in developing certain social indicators which project the probability of growth rates and inflation, etc. An expert in accountancy, psychology, architecture, life science, and chemistry can give exact interpretations of his ideas and objectives by drawing inferences from the data he collected from the field. In addition to the professional aspects of Mathematics, it also plays a vital role in the life of the common man where certain numerals and calculations are essential for the management of life in the market economy.

In modern society, Mathematics functions as central to technological development in contributing to the knowledge economy in terms of medicine and financial services. It forms the fundamental basis for scientific and industrial development. Mathematics is highly becoming central to the market economy, especially in developing certain games like Puzzles,

Riddles, Ludo, Sudoku, and Crosswords. Extension to this computer-based games like Video Games, Pubg, and other games associated with Football, Cricket, and Hockey are generating huge wealth when the potential age group of youth between 14-20 years is targeted in generating the income. In the other sense, Calculation, Algorithm, and Symmetry are highly utilized in developing the above games.

Mathematics in Analyzing the Living Standards

Mathematics helps man in standardize certain parameters like Health, Nutrition, Calories, the volume of medicines and life expectancy rates, etc. It helps in calculating estimating and defining the Poverty and Unemployment levels. When these calculations are studied concerning the food supply, agricultural wealth, and a variety of crops grown would help the economists in customizing certain standards for different sections of society. It helps the policymakers to focus on critical areas in which much funding is to be allotted. It helps the analysts in categorizing certain sectors which need priority in terms of development.

Conclusion

The major emphasis duly measured through the spectrum of Mathematics helps society in knowing the factual information in identifying the areas, which are to be given due priority when analyzed by using mathematical knowledge. Henceforth, Mathematics as a discipline though not much recognized by mainstream society but broadly plays a greater role in understanding the process of development and helps policymakers to develop certain patterns in organizing the natural resources for the development of society.

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